

Studies on Fluorocomplexes of Beryllium

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Solubilities of fluoberyllates of Ni(II), Co(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Mg(II) at different temperatures have been studied. Magnesium fluoberyllate and magnesium ammonium fluoberyllate have been prepared for the first time. The transition temperatures of the divalent metal fluoberyllates have been determined from the solubility curves.

Ray¹ found that if the fluoberyllates of Ni(II) and Co(II) are crystallised at 0° the crystals are heptahydrated and when crystallised at room temperature they are hexahydrated. No detailed investigation was made on the solubility transition temperature relationship.

Steele and Johnson² determined the transition temperature of heptahydrated nickel sulfate to hexahydrated nickel sulfate from its solubility curve. The hexahydrate has been shown to exist in two forms (α and β). The transition temperatures are

According to Chertin and Rohmer³, the corresponding temperatures are 29.1° and 63.3° respectively. J. Koppel and H. Wetzel⁴ found that $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystallises from solution below 40.7°. C. D. Carpenter and E. R. Jette⁵ mentioned this temperature to be 45.1°. The solubilities of copper sulfate in water has been measured by many workers⁶⁻¹⁰. Cohen¹¹ from the solubility curve of zinc sulfate, determined the transition temperature to be 39°, above which the hexahydrate crystallises out. Mylius and Funk¹² determined the solubility of cadmium sulfate at different temperatures and concluded that above 74°, a monohydrate exists. The transition temperature for hepta- to hexahydrate of magnesium sulfate is 48.2°.^{13,14}

1. N. N. Ray, *Z. anorg. u. allge. chem.*, 1932, **205**, 257.
2. Steele and Johnson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 113.
3. Chertin and Rohmer, *Compt. rend.*, 1934, **198**, 92.
4. J. Koppel and H. Wetzel, *Zeit. Phys. Chem.*, 1905, **52**, 169.
5. C. D. Carpenter and E. R. Jette, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 583.
6. T. Gruner and R. Bendes, *Trommsdorff's Jour.*, 1826, **12**, 92.
7. L. C. de Coppet, *Zeit. Phys. Chem.*, 1897, **22**, 239.
8. J. E. Trevor, *ibid.*, 1891, **7**, 470.
9. E. Cohen, *ibid.*, 1899, **31**, 173.
10. A. Etard, *Compt. rend.*, 1887, **104**, 1615; 1892, **114**, 112.
11. Cohen, *Zeit. Phys. Chem.*, 1900, **34**, 182.
12. Mylius and Funk, *Ber.*, 1897, **30**, 824.
13. Van't Hoff, Meyerhoffer and Smith, *Sitzber. Akad. Berlin*, 1901, 1034.
14. E. Wiedemann, *Wied. Ann.*, 1882, **17**, 571.

In view of the close analogy of the fluoberyllates with sulfates it was considered desirable to undertake a study of the solubility curves of nickel, cobalt, copper, zinc, cadmium and magnesium fluoberyllates and to determine the transition temperatures. As the fluoberyllates undergo slight decomposition in solution at high temperatures, on account of hydrolysis, solubility measurements beyond 40° were not made.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of fluoberyllates : All the bivalent metal fluoberyllates e.g. copper fluoberyllate, cobalt fluoberyllate, nickel fluoberyllate, zinc fluoberyllate, cadmium fluoberyllate were prepared according to the method of Ray¹. Magnesium fluoberyllate and its double salt of the Schönies series e.g., magnesium ammonium fluoberyllate have been isolated by the authors for the first time.

Magnesium fluoberyllate, $MgBeF_4 \cdot 6H_2O$: The compound was prepared by the metathesis reaction between equivalent amounts of thallos fluoberyllate and magnesium chloride, keeping magnesium chloride in slight excess. The precipitated thallos chloride was filtered off, and the filtrate was crystallised in a vacuum desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 at 0°. The transparent shining white crystals obtained were filtered and dried between folds of filter paper.

0.3638 gm of the substance gave 0.0406 g of BeO and 0.2592 g of CaF_2 . 0.1348 g, of the same material required 5.95 ml of 0.1044 (M) EDTA solution for estimation of magnesium. Found Mg = 11.21%, Be = 4.01%, F = 34.75%. Calculated for $MgBeF_4 \cdot 6H_2O$, Mg = 11.19%; Be = 4.14%; F = 34.97%.

Magnesium ammonium fluoberyllate, $(NH_4)_2BeF_4, MgBeF_4, 6H_2O$: A sample of magnesium fluoberyllate (about 1 g.) was mixed with 0.5 gm of ammonium fluoberyllate in aqueous solution (molar ratio of about 1 : 1). The solution was then crystallised in a vacuum desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 . The crystals obtained were filtered and dried between folds of a filter paper.

FIG 1 SOLUBILITY CURVES.

0.1616 g. of the material on analysis gave 0.0830 g of BaBeF_4 and 0.0562 g. of the same substance required 16.4 ml of 0.01044 (*M*) EDTA solution for estimation of magnesium. Found, Mg = 7.29% BeF_4^{2-} = 19.63%. Calculated for, $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{BeF}_4$, MgBeF_4 , $6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Mg = 7.19%; BeF_4^{2-} = 20.00%.

TABLE 1

Nickel fluoberyllate

Temperature °C	Solubility in gms. of NiBeF_4 (anhydrous) per 100 gms. of water	Composition of the solid
9	35.38	$\text{NiBeF}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$
12	36.02	"
15	36.39	"
18	37.56	"
21	38.00	$\text{NiBeF}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$
24	38.46	"
27	38.66	"
30	39.82	"
33	40.66	"
36	41.79	"
39	43.80	"

Determination of solubilities : Saturated solutions with adequate residual solid were prepared with individual compounds in small Jena-glass bottles and were placed in a thermostat within a temperature recording an accuracy of $\pm 0.5^\circ$ and fitted with mechanical shaking device. After the attaining of equilibrium, within approximately a week or two the clear liquid from the top was quickly transferred by rapid filtration to a previously weighed sample bottle and was analysed as usual. The solid residue separated at the bottom was also analysed from time to time. Measurements were made at different temperatures and the results are given in Tables 1 to 6. Solubility curves are shown in figures 1 and 2.

TABLE 2

Cobalt fluoberyllate

Temperature °C	Solubility in gms. of CoBeF ₄ (anhydrous) per 100 gms. of water	Composition of the solid
0	21.81	CoBeF ₄ .7H ₂ O
5	22.00	„
10	22.84	„
15	23.96	„
20	25.87	CoBeF ₄ .6H ₂ O
25	25.94	„
30	27.81	„
35	28.87	„
40	30.22	„

TABLE 3

Copper fluoberyllate

Temperature °C	Solubility in gms. of CuBeF ₄ (anhydrous) per 100 gms. of water	Composition of the solid
0	23.39	CuBeF ₄ .5H ₂ O
5	23.82	„
10	24.94	„
15	26.19	„
20	27.35	„
25	28.67	„
30	30.12	„
35	32.24	„
40	34.56	„

TABLE 4

Zinc fluoberyllate

Temperature °C	Solubility in gms. of ZnBeF ₄ (anhydrous) per 100 gms. of water	Composition of the solid
0	36.25	ZnBeF ₄ .7H ₂ O
5	38.62	„
10	42.28	„
15	46.34	„
20	50.42	ZnBeF ₄ .6H ₂ O
25	53.08	„
30	59.72	„
35	65.54	„
40	71.48	„

TABLE 5

Cadmium fluoberyllate

Temperature °C	Solubility in gms. of CdBeF ₄ (anhydrous) per 100 gms. of water	Composition of the solid
0	31.90	CdBeF ₄ .8/3H ₂ O
5	—	„
10	35.12	„
15	36.95	„
20	39.00	„
25	40.44	„
30	41.92	„
35	43.02	„
40	44.89	„

DISCUSSION

The solubility curves of the bivalent fluoberyllates of nickel, cobalt and zinc show transitions, the respective transition temperatures being 19°, 18°, 18° respectively. From their close analogy with the corresponding sulfates, it is probable that the transitions are due to the change over from the heptahydrated form (stable at lower temperature) to the hexahydrated form (stable at higher temperature). The solubility curves for CuBeF₄ and

TABLE 6

Magnesium fluoberyllate

Temperature °C	Solubility in gms. of MgBeF ₄ (anhydrous) per 100 gms. of water	Composition of the solid
0	22.08	MgBeF ₄ .6H ₂ O
5	23.63	„
10	24.52	„
15	26.00	„
20	28.68	„
25	30.95	„
30	34.20	„
35	38.52	„
40	42.03	„

MgBeF₄, show no transitions within the temperature range 0–40°. Therefore CuBeF₄.5H₂O and MgBeF₄.6H₂O are stable within this temperature range. The transition shown in the solubility curves for CdBeF₄ is probably due to two forms, the α -CdBeF₄ and β -CdBeF₄, as the chemical analysis of the solid phase at 0° and 35° showed no other hydrate except CdBeF₄. 8/3 H₂O.

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Received August 3, 1970